
THE JUPITER PROJECT: WHITE PAPER

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Jupiter is a set of tools and resources to develop computer systems to manage health care operations. It is not a single computer system, but an infrastructure to design information management systems quickly and efficiently adaptable to different needs and environments. Such systems include:

- Hospital-wide electronic-medical-record systems.
- Clinical trial management system.
- Laboratory information systems.
- Quality management programmes.
- Inventory management.
- Scheduling.
- Billing.
- Compliance.
- Training and competency.
- Clinical research datasets.
- Inter-system interfaces.
- Interfaces between instruments and information systems.

The main asset in The Jupiter Project is ***The Jupiter Software Design Infrastructure***, which is used to design customised computer systems that meet the specific needs of a health care enterprise. Each health care facility has its unique needs and requirement that cannot be addressed by a universal general system.

The objective of The Jupiter Project is to create customised computer systems that:

1. Facilitate the clinical decision-making process.
2. Improve the quality of health care, reducing errors and improving clinical outcome.
3. Provide data analysis tools to give access to medical knowledge and to produce new medical knowledge.

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF HEALTH CARE

In the developed world one of the main frustration of physicians is the poor presentation of clinical data, which often blurs the necessary information to make adequate clinical decisions. Often such data is unclear and difficult to retrieve. The respond they get to their requests for improvements in data presentation in the electronic medical record in use in their institutions is often that 'it cannot be done'. The typical attitude in hospital administration is that if it cannot be done then it won't be done. On the contrary, the attitude of physicians is that if the EMR in place cannot do it, then alternative ways must be explored to present data in the most accessible and clearest possible manner.

This has been one of our main motivations in creating The Jupiter Project: to give access to physicians to clinical data in the most accessible and clearest possible manner to facilitate the clinical decision-making process. Of course, we pay extreme attention to the administrative functions of an EMR, like documentation, auditing, billing, compliance, etc., but our main focus is to provide the most useful tools to make clinical decisions.

In investigating the cause of iatrogenic errors, mistakes and accidents, poor access to data, lack of fool-proof clinical decision-making tools, and poor documentation are often identified as key features of the systemic problems in the health care industry.

Without overlooking other factors, we see the electronic medical record as one of the most pragmatic tools to improve the quality of health care.

QUALITY IN CLINICAL MANAGEMENT

Our commitment to quality in health care is revealed in the various quality tools our systems provide:

- automated documentation
- data audits for internal consistency
- data controls for external consistency
- proficiency
- personnel qualifications, training, and competency
- personnel data access and data manipulation privileges
- data access transparency
- communication centre
- variance manager (errors, mistakes, accidents, failures, etc.)

PRINCIPLES OF CLINICAL DATA MANAGEMENT

Every patient produces information that can be used to improve his and other patient's health.

Knowledge derived from empirical data is built on data relations at different levels:

- within a patient at a given time
- within a patient over time
- among patients
- within the scope of clinical epidemiology
- within the scope of genetic epidemiology
- in connection with specialised data sets of different kinds for medical diagnosis, infectious agents, pharmaceutical drugs, anatomical and histological entities, genetic variants, medical procedures, etc.

Health care providers should not only be the consumers of medical knowledge, but also the producers of medical knowledge. From this perspective electronic medical records and clinical management systems

should be designed so that practitioners not only have easy access to medical knowledge, but also have access to the tools to produce new medical knowledge. The latter is accomplished with the aid of data analysis based on such methods as machine learning and pattern recognition.

HEALTH LITERACY

The Jupiter Project Team is dedicated to helping patients and health care providers make better clinical decisions. The starting point to achieve this goal is to promote health literacy among both patients and health care providers.

We are committed to promote access to the best health clinical data. We are in the process of establishing partnerships with some of the best medical education institutions to create the tools to support this access. In addition, we have developed educational tools for both patients and clinical staff to get familiar with medical knowledge, making an emphasis on evidence-based medical practice.

We have closely followed the psychology empirical work done by Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky on judgement under uncertainty. We are aware of the difficulties in making decisions based on probabilities, particularly conditional probabilities and make every effort to present clinical data in the simplest and clearest possible manner. For instance, we favour 2x2 contingency tables with raw numbers rather than probabilities as the ideal tool to evaluate risks and outcomes.

CLINICAL RISK INFORMATION

The foundation of all clinical decisions, by both patients and health care providers, is based on the critical evaluation of clinical risk information. In reviewing diagnostic tests and evaluation procedures (radiology, etc.), results must be examined in terms of how they affect clinical risks. Clinical risk information tables must be integral component of the patient's medical record. In order to compare difference treatment options, for instance, their clinical risks themselves must be evaluated and compared. We have not economised efforts to develop the best clinical-risk data structures to present such risks, taking into account the limitations of humans to grasp the true meaning of probabilities, especially conditional probabilities.

MULTI-CENTRE RESEARCH DATA-SHARING INITIATIVE

Jupiter is committed to help health care centres make contributions to medical knowledge. This commitment shows up in three ways:

- Making available the *Jupiter Clinical Trial Management System* to health care centres.
- Integrating the different data management systems with each other within a health care institution.
- Opening up the *Jupiter Electronic Medical Record* for multi-centre data sharing.

CLINICAL PATHWAYS AND LOGICAL CLINICAL DECISION TREES

Modern medicine is based on (1) the standardisation of clinical protocols, where clinical decisions are not improvised but are formalised in established protocols, and (2) the documentation of adherence or deviation from these protocols in the care of each patient. A fundamental aspect of an electronic medical record and clinical management system designed for the practice of this kind of modern medicine is the central key role of standard clinical pathways, which are clinical decision logical trees. Patient care must be based on formalised (computerised) decision logical trees.

Therefore, modern clinical information systems must provide the tools to:

- Represent in computational models to be used by clinical applications the clinical pathways and clinical decision trees in use.
- Link the progress of each patient to a specific position in these clinical-decision-tree models. At the same time, forcing the proper documentation of any deviation from standard established protocols.

Our Logical-Clinical-Decision-Tree module provides such tools.

The Jupiter System is a tool for clinical reasoning.

COMPUTER SYSTEMS WITH BUILT-IN INTELLIGENCE

Our clinical information systems, which we call *The Jupiter Project*, are not just data repositories, they primarily provide data structures for storing data in a logical manner that facilitates retrieval and further processing.

Our team of computer scientists specialise in building into our systems domain-specific automated intelligence. As an example, see attached document 'Theory of reference values.pdf' with a description of a computational model of medical diagnosis based on the theory of reference values. This is the original core of a series of computer tools to automate medical diagnosis. Similar systems can also be used for patient management and medical treatment.

For a more sophisticated example of built-in intelligence based on propositional logic used in our systems, see the document 'Propositional calculus of gene expression.pdf'.

THE JUPITER SOFTWARE DESIGN INFRASTRUCTURE

These are proprietary secret tools to which Jupiter has exclusive access. They include:

- High-level programming languages to address the needs of health-care operations. These languages are implemented as functions, procedures and classes organised as object-programming-language computer libraries.
- Carefully designed data structures to hold the various types of complicated data produced in health care. These are at the central core of the Jupiter Design Infrastructure. The algorithms used

for data manipulation depend on the data structures developed. Data structures limit the kind of algorithms you can use, for this reason at Jupiter we do not save resources in the developing and perfecting the best data structures possible.

- Algorithms based on machine learning techniques and sophisticated pattern recognition, using publicly known and proprietary and secret methods.
- *Code Machines*—our term to refer to computer programmes that write computer code. This is one of the critical keys in our capacity to design, develop and deploy customised product quickly and efficiently, reducing coding errors to a bare minimum.
- Man-machine interfaces that define how the user interacts with a computer system. These interfaces are developed based on cognitive psychology principles and are the key for the prevention of clerical errors that are very common in health care and can cause great expenses and damage to patients.

In addition, our working infrastructure also includes other widely known tools such as:

- Machine-machine interfaces to transfer data among computer systems. (Using the JSON and the XML standards.)
- Machine-machine networking for procedure communication.
- Strict adherence to the Codd relational model in database design.
- Use of stored procedures (SQL) within a database to manipulate data rather than building SQL queries in the application.
- HTML 5, including SVG, JavaScript and jQuery in the production of reports, rather than other less efficient tools such as PDF documents.
- Microsoft Visual Studio as the programming environment and SQL Server for database management.
- R for statistics and mathematical processing.

CONNECTIVITY

One of our priorities is to develop systems with a distributed-computing approach. Rather than having centralised databases with single owners, we favour independent domain-related databases where those who produce the data control the data.

As a result, connectivity between systems becomes of central importance and we specialise in developing interfaces with multiple systems, including equipment, liquid handlers, as well as hospital-level electronic-medical-record systems.

We use the following connectivity and networking tools.

- Direct database-to-database connections using ‘stored procedures’ for specialised queries and ‘views’ for generic queries.
- TCP-IP networking for closed one-to-one connections.
- HTTP networking for open but secured many-to-many connections.

- File sharing, FTP etc., by means of JASON and XML files.

INTEGRATION

This initiative includes a number of products:

- Electronic medical records
- Personal clinical record (for individual patients)
- Laboratory information system
- Clinical trial management system

One of our main goals is to create an integrated system where the information produced in different health care activities can be linked to each other. All the systems mentioned above are designed in such a way so as to make data transmission and integration seamless.

SECURITY AND ENCRYPTION

We have set security as a top priority. It is our position that the key to success in this difficult aspect of computer systems is the design of data structures. Data structures must be defined with security in mind. Security cannot be an afterthought.

Security would be trivial if data sharing were not an issue, but in health care data must be shared constantly. For this reason, it is critical to separate privacy and HIPAA-protected data elements from other data elements.

In our systems data needs not be de-identified because it is organised in a de-identified manner following our data structures.

We do not outsource encryption. Our cryptography engineers produce our own encryption protocols using public-key-private-key for maximum security messages and symmetric-key encryption for standard-level security needs.

Depending on the size of the project our databases can be designed with the possibility of merging data from separate database using UUID for primary and foreign keys.

HUMAN-MACHINE INTERACTION

In the design of the user interface in our applications we give priority to the efficient interaction of humans with the information systems.

From the beginnings in the history of computers, even before the first commercial products were in the market, even before Steve Jobs and Bill Gates were born, two different attitudes towards computers were being adopted: 1) *artificial intelligence*, and 2) *augmented intelligence*. Marvin Minsky and John McCarty developed the first approach in the hope of having machines that could learn on their own and mimic human intelligence. JCR Licklider and Doug Engelbart develop the second approach with the symbiosis

between man and computer in mind. We subscribe to this second *augmented intelligence* approach in which the true value of computers is revealed in the human-machine interaction, rather than in computers designed to outperform humans in intellectual tasks. It is with the background of this belief in *augmented intelligence* that we design all our computer systems.

TECHNICAL SUPPORT

Customer relations and technical support is one of our main priorities. We value technical support as much as the quality of our products.

THE RIGHT BUSINESS ORGANISATION

In his book *Creativity, Inc.* Ed Catmull makes a poignant presentation of his reaction to the success of the first major product in the company he had created. Instead of being satisfied with the success, he was worried about creating the right organisation to handle the implications of this success.

Similarly, in our starting company our main worry is to create the right organisation to bring our products to our customers. We know the product we have in our hand is a first-rate quality product, but how can we produce similar products to meet the demand?

There are three main questions in creating a company: 'Why?', 'What?' and 'How?'. The first refers to the motivation and that is very clear to us, the second is the product we have to offer, and we have great confidence in it, but the third is how to make it and we are struggling to address it.

The reason many start-up companies fail is because they get excited about the 'why' and the 'what', but forget about the 'how'. They may have a top-of-the-line product, but they haven't come up with a method to produce it efficiently and competitively and to create new similar products.

At this point we have a better idea about what kind of organisation we don't want than the one we want. One of the main reasons our competitors fail to address the demands of their customers is the large size and rigidity of their business organisation models. The first thing you need to realise is that writing good quality software is a creative process, and a creative enterprise cannot be managed by large hierarchical teams, small flat open flexible teams are necessary instead. All attempts to follow rigid standard operating procedures to create innovative top-quality software have failed. This is the best well-kept secret of the software industry.

Being aware that this is our main challenge, we are committed to spare no resources in creating the best possible business organisation model to produce and to put in the market our products.

In these early stages we know one thing: the best approach is to create small independent units where our software engineers will operate with a level of freedom not seen in our industry. This is the price we must pay to have the best and most innovative products.

CREATIVITY AND INNOVATION DOES NOT PRECLUDE QUALITY

A vertical hierarchy and rigidity are imposed on the software industry in the name of safety, quality, and security. The idea is that tight control of the production process is the best way to control the outcome properties. Safety, quality, and security, however, are emergent properties in complex systems and no amount of control on production is a guarantee to have any control on these or other emergent properties. For this reason, our first principle in our quality philosophy is parsimony: make it small and make it simple; if it must be complex, then make it small; if it must be large, then make it simple; but under no circumstance make a software application that is large and complex, that is a sure recipe for disaster. We look at the products we are competing against with amazement as we see how big and complex they are. We are certainly not surprised to hear about implementation disasters in the news from time to time, or consumer frustration in using these products. There is certainly a gap in the market for simple flexible systems to address the demands of an industry with critical information management needs.

We come from a tradition of commitment to total quality as originally promoted by W. Edwards Deming in manufacturing industries. Deming's quality principles are the core of our business philosophy and define all aspects of our operations and organisational model.

Creativity and innovation do not preclude quality, in fact, they can be the key to real quality. And they can because there is no universal recipe for quality, quality itself is a creative process. Quality cannot be imposed from above, it must certainly be encouraged and supported from above, but its details and implementation must come from production workers, from representatives in the field, from customer support teams, from everybody at all levels. Quality is almost impossible to implement in a top-down organisational model.

THE SOURCE OF CREATIVITY

The University of Chicago psychologist Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi has dedicated a significant portion of his career to study the psychological processes behind creativity and has identified a state of mind he calls 'flow'. A business enterprise that relies on a creative process, like, in our case, the design and development of computer programmes, must take these findings seriously.

We realise that our success depends on creating a working environment where the psychological conditions for creativity, as studied by Csikszentmihalyi, are promoted and given priority.

COLLABORATIVE LEARNING COMMUNITIES

Another of our fundamental philosophical guiding principles is the following: The only way to success in anything is by collaborating with the best. Establishing fruitful relationships with the best in a field is the sure way to get something done that ends up being worth doing. Our goal is therefore straightforward: to create and promote collaborative learning communities. We understand this as the opposite of a bureaucracy, with its rigidity and hierarchy. Establishing relationships of all kinds with customers, other companies in the supply chain, employees, etc. is always the same thing: opening doors for collaboration,

establishing mutually beneficial relationships between equals. (Jean-Jacques Rousseau's concept of social contract)

We understand how difficult this is. That is why we are ready to spare no pain in achieving this goal.

And we understand that this depends on trust, the most elusive of qualities in all relationships. And in trying to decipher the meaning of trust and in coming to a series of its elements such as loyalty, solidarity, tolerance, transparency, openness etc., we cannot but conclude that in the end it is not really a question of finding the right recipe for the ideal organisational structure. The real question is the moral integrity of the members of a community.

Therefore, we have the two basic elements: 1) the ideal social organisational structure and 2) the moral integrity of the members in that society. It is an established fact that the first affects the second, but it is also a fact, although not established and even less recognised, that the second creates the first. And if the first element is difficult to find it is because the second element is absent.

At any rate, difficult and elusive as this subject might be, one thing is clear, individualism, closing the door of collaboration, does not lead to anything good. Something else is also clear, the group perspective, without taking into account the value of each individual, is empty. It is only in the dialectics between the individual and the group that we can find ourselves on the road to building the ideal business organisational structure. The solution is not a theoretical solution, but a pragmatic one.

JUPITER CODE OF ETHICS

The Jupiter Project is based on a number of fundamental principles:

1. Regarding iatrogenesis (ill effects of health care):
 - a. Each error, mistake or accident must be fully documented and investigated.
 - b. There must be full transparency in regard to errors, mistakes, and accidents in health care.
 - c. Once an iatrogenic event has been identified and investigated, measures must be taken to prevent similar events in the future. These measures must be evaluated as to their effectiveness.
2. Regarding patient access to their medical records:
 - a. Patients must be involved in all critical clinical decisions and this involvement must be documented.
 - b. Medical records should be accurate, complete, simple, and clear. They must totally rely on computer files and databases. No paper documentation is allowed.
 - c. Every interaction with a patient, every procedure, every test, must be documented.
 - d. Patients are the owners of their health information and all records associated with it.
 - e. Patients have the right to control who has access to their medical records.
 - f. To provide health care, providers need full access to the patient's medical record.
 - g. Both patients and their corresponding health care providers must be able to see who has access to the patient's medical records and for what period of time.

- h. Every item in the medical record must have an author and a date of creation. Later modifications must be documented.

Jupiter is committed to creating:

- a user-friendly medical record access management system
- auditing tools for medical record access
- a user-friendly consent documentation system

A HISTORY OF SUCCESSES IN BUILDING CLINICAL MANAGEMENT COMPUTER SYSTEMS

The Jupiter Project has put together a computer science team that over the years has developed a number of computer systems serving different needs in different facilities using what we now call *The Jupiter Design Infrastructure*. This history of successful computer system implementations includes:

1. A bacteria-antibiotic-resistance monitoring system that managed the control of antibiotic resistance in a large hospital. (*Michael Reese Hospital*. Chicago 1988)
2. A SNOMED-based autopsy database. (*Michael Reese Hospital*. Chicago 1988)
3. A variance manager to keep track of errors, mistakes and accidents in a large hospital blood bank. (*University of Maryland Medical System*. Baltimore 1994)
4. A rule-out-panel expert system to address a complex time-consuming operation in a blood bank. (*University of Maryland Medical System*. Baltimore 1995)
5. *Banderas*, a man-machine interface to identify samples and facilitate their recognition in the laboratory to prevent clerical errors. (Baltimore 1998. Later implemented in *MD Anderson Cancer Center* reducing the number of sample switches from 1/3000 to zero.)
6. Peptide-binding-prediction models. A system used in multiple research and clinical applications, including the design of vaccines. (Developed under an NIH R01 grant. Baltimore 1999)
7. Complex-data-analysis tools based on propositional logic. Research tools used in the interpretation of large data sets from gene expression microarray chip technology. (Developed under an NIH R01 grant. Houston 2000)
8. *Project 2*, a full-fledged laboratory information system for an HLA typing laboratory in the largest centre for bone-marrow transplantation. (*MD Anderson Cancer Center*. Houston 2003)
9. *HLA HUB*, a multisystem interface to manage data flow back and forth from different instruments and computer systems. (*HLA Typing Laboratory, Stanford University*. Palo Alto, CA 2011)
10. *Daedalus*, an inter-department information system to bring HLA-typing data and histocompatibility expertise to the bedside of a major bone-marrow -transplant programme. (*Moffitt Cancer Center*, Tampa, FL 2016)
11. Next-generation-sequencing data pipeline manager. This tool brings under control the complex data accumulated with this innovative technique. (*Moffitt Cancer Center*, Tampa, FL 2018)

